

ANTHROPOCENTRISM IN THE MASS MEDIA

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Abstract: Anthropocentrism in the mass media refers to the tendency of media outlets to prioritize human interests and perspectives over those of other living beings or the environment. This bias often manifests in the way stories are framed, with human-centric narratives taking precedence and non-human entities being portrayed primarily in relation to their impact on humans.

Keywords: anthropocentric paradigm, virtual environment, mass media, competence, cultural linguistics, concept, globalization, human consciousness, lexical lacunae.

Today we live in a global world that is characterized by a high degree of information. The relevance of media linguistics as a new systematic approach to the study of the media language is due to the fact that media texts are today, one of the most common forms of language existence. Indeed, the second half of the XX–beginning of the XXI century is characterized by the rapid growth of a new sphere of speech consumption and mass communication. Dynamic development of traditional media: print, radio, television, the emergence of new computer information technology, the globalization of the world’s information space has a huge impact on the production and distribution of words. All these complex and multifaceted processes require not only scientific understanding but also the development of new paradigms for practical research of the of the media language .²³ Virtual environment is a subsystem consisting of the following components: a) technical equipment of workplaces with information technology; b) hypertext databases; c) virtual communication environment. The technical equipment of workplaces is provided by means of communication, means of preparing electronic educational resources. Virtual communication environment - electronic correspondence, conferences and forums, chats, virtual consulting services and others, organized through Internet access. Today, it is relevant to create a special information and communication professional educational environment for teaching foreign languages to students of

²³ VASILIEVA, A. (1982). “Newspaper-journalistic style of speech”. Russian language. Russia.

higher educational institutions. In this case, the information and communication professional educational environment acts as a system for the formation of personality in the process of acquiring professional and foreign language competencies, as well as the opportunities for their development by means of information and communication. One of the components of the information and communication professional educational environment is the information and communication component, which is represented by various information and communication technologies, learning tools and solving educational problems, software, electronic educational platforms that contribute to the development of professional competencies and is a means of acquiring foreign language skills. It follows that, along with foreign language professional competence, students should also develop information competence. Of particular importance is the use of information and communication technologies designed to ensure the implementation of innovative forms and methods that can help identify and develop the competencies of students while mastering the English language. Today, information and communication technologies can be used in all areas of activity and professional fields, and are thus becoming increasingly integrated into the system of higher professional education. It is worth noting that one of the important results of the use of information and communication technologies in the field of education is distance learning, which in the age of development and popularization of information technologies has become widespread in education, since it makes it possible to obtain knowledge at a distance. Thus, distance learning is an information and educational system of remote access based on modern information technologies. Today, distance learning is one of the most dynamically developing areas in education. The difference between distance education and traditional education is the distance between the teacher and the student and the lack of their direct contact during the learning process. In this regard, the traditional form of education will always have an advantage, no matter how perfect the technical basis for transmitting information is. It must be emphasized that the introduction of information and communication technologies makes it possible to move to a qualitatively different level of education, due to new pedagogical technologies and methods. Distance learning involves the use of information technology, network and virtual learning, which allows the educational process to be carried out in a virtual environment using the Internet. Internet technologies are the technological basis of distance learning, which is associated with the increased capabilities of technical means of communication and the spread of social networks.

The study and analysis of scientific literature on the problem of developing foreign language professional information and communication competence based on the use of social networks in the educational process showed the presence of different directions of its research. This is a communicative approach that reveals language as a means of communication; a cognitive approach aimed at developing critical thinking and the ability to clearly and express one's point of view in situations of professional and business communication; a competency-based approach related to the order for education from employers and the needs of modern society; modular training, which emphasizes the activity-based approach - the essence of this training is the complete independence of the student in achieving specific goals of educational and cognitive activity. In the study, we also relied on the work of foreign scientists on the problem of developing professional communicative competence. To form foreign language professional competence on the basis of only existing manuals, without attracting additional funds and developing various and methodologically appropriate techniques, methods and forms of work is, in our opinion, neither rational nor effective. In this regard, the need to increase the efficiency of language training through the development and implementation of innovative information communication technologies in the learning process, namely social networks, as well as the latest teaching methods, is obvious. The social demand in relation to language education has changed over a number of decades, but its main meaning has always been reduced to mastering a foreign language. The very concept of "practical mastery of a foreign language" was refined as the methodology of teaching foreign languages developed. Among the many competencies that are considered mandatory in the training of professionals in any field, the competency associated with proficiency in a foreign language is presented in different formulations, but at the same time, as a rule, reflects the requirement to demonstrate the ability or be willing to communicate orally and in writing in native and foreign languages, cultural skills of social and professional communication. The term communicative competence is widely used in the methodology as an indicator of the level of. Linguistic competence: the subject's speech literacy; degree of fluency in a foreign language; variety of language used (lexical, grammatical, phonetic, spelling); imagery, expressiveness, idiomatic speech. Speech competence: success in all types of speech activity; mastery of various methods of argumentation, forms of presentation of thoughts (analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalization); a variety of ways to connect speech and expressive techniques to achieve the goal of communication. Sociocultural competence: knowledge of the culture of the native and studied languages; the ability to analyze

the experience of cultural development of the native country and the country of the language being studied in the interaction of their cultures, as well as to trace its reflection in the languages of both countries; presence/absence of sociolinguistic and sociocultural difficulties in the communication process; taking into account the norms of formal and informal communication in oral and written speech. Discursive competence: the ability to understand various types of communicative statements, as well as to construct holistic, coherent and logical statements of different functional styles to achieve the goal of communication; the correct choice of linguistic means depending on the type of utterance. Strategic competence: the ability to use verbal and non-verbal strategies to compensate for failures in the communication process due to language deficits and increase the effectiveness of communication. Social competence: the ability and desire to interact with communication partners; the ability to help another maintain communication, put oneself in his place, and cope with situations that arise in the process of misunderstanding between participants in communication. Professional competence: the ability to successfully use acquired and developed foreign language knowledge, skills and abilities for professional purposes, in the process of language learning. Based on the analysis of methodological literature, the principles of teaching the lexical side of speech, the principles of selecting lexical units for the formation of a lexical minimum, it is possible to formulate requirements for a set of exercises for the development of foreign language professional competence.

The globalization of the world information space has contributed not only to a significant expansion of the sphere of influence of the English language but also to its transformation into a universally recognized language of international communication – lingua franca. Currently, English has become the language of international business and trade, politics and diplomacy, science and information technology, mass media, popular music, show business, sports, and education. Today, it is hardly possible to find a field of human activity in which the English language does not have a dominant meaning. The global role of the English language in the modern world is perfectly described by the famous English linguist²⁴ in the book *English as a Global Language*, noting the role of the media in the promotion and dissemination of the English language and mass culture in the national media landscape²⁵. Indeed, the total number of media texts in English distributed daily

²⁴ CRYSTAL, D. (1996). "English as a Global Language". RoutledgeUK

²⁵ LYSAKOVA, I. (1989). "Type of newspaper and publication style: experience of sociolinguistic research". Saint Petersburg, the publishing house of Saint Petersburg University. Russia.

through mass media channels significantly exceeds the number of texts in other languages, and in the national mass media of almost all countries of the world, there is an expansion of samples of English-language mass culture.

The concept of common information space is crucial for understanding the dynamics of language change, as it allows us to provide the multi-faceted activity of world and national mass media in the form of a single, integrated system, functioning which has a significant impact on the flow of linguacultural processes. In modern science, to designate this new virtual territory without state borders and tangible barriers, a whole set of terms and concepts are used, referring to the same semantic line, but emphasizing one or another side of mass communication processes, such as information space, information environment, information field, media environment, media landscape, infosphere.

Here, attention is focused on such important quantitative indicators as changing the number of speakers in a particular language, the redistribution of language spheres of influence, increasing the role of some, and reducing the role of other languages in the world information space. Such as, the language of mass media is the entire body of texts produced and distributed by mass media, especially in the messages. In the messages, the people use emoticons instead of words. An emoticon is a symbol, most often used in computer-mediated communications, that is intended to represent a facial expression that communicates the emotional state of the author. The word emoticons is a combination of the words emotion and icon. Emoticons are punctuation marks, letters, and numbers used to create pictorial icons that generally display an emotion or sentiment. An emoticon is a sequence of keyboard characters used to illustrate a facial expression or to render some kind of picture or symbol, such as, here are the most popular emoticons²⁶:

- :-) smile, joy
- :-(sadness, sadness
- : - | thoughtfulness or neutrality,
- :-D laughter,: - \ puzzling or resentment
- : -0, = -O, 8-O,: - [] surprise (open mouth)
- : - [embarrassment
- >: - D malicious laughter
- : ‘- D strong laughter, laughter to tears D-: strong anger, anger
- ;-) wink

²⁶ www.google.com. Emojislife.com

:-P, :-p,: -b show the tongue

: - * kiss

Emoticons denote international concepts, so they do not reproduce current speech, do not reflect grammatical, phonetic, and other features of natural language. Emoticons are a direct tool for forming an impression of the author's position or his personality. Earlier when the field of Internet communication was just beginning to be formed (the main forms of early web communication were conferences and chats), researchers of computer-mediated communication conducted an analysis of the behavior of chat moderators. As a result, it was revealed that the use of emoticons by moderators contributed to the perception by Internet users as more «dynamic», «friendly», «useful» and «inclined to communicate» compared to those who did not use smiles.

If the people do not the slangs or abbreviations they are not able to understand such kind of messages. Specifically in the dialogue of comments abbreviations, emoticons, symbols, orthoepic spelling, simplification of grammatical constructions are actively applied. Let us consider for example the following communicative situation. The start post is devoted to online purchases:

“Tonight brought another order for Victoria Secret, of course, as always, all the essentials you can purchase. Could you ever live without pants with peacocks, with a 70% discount? OMG, sale be over soon. Here it is, the vegetable life of the nursing mother. Girlies, join, hit the sales of the family budget! I am a little amateur in the middle of my life”.

The tendency to the oral language can be even more tangible in the comments:

- maxryta: I love this brand :))

- nucamb_no_necky: but I still can not get acquainted with outlet inet-shopping))) and thanx God))

- kengu_ry: I'm here, stunned by the instinct of self and child preservation, want to buy a rope ladder. Just in case that is on sale. That's it. Never found :)))

- zoe_dorogaya: For a hundred rubles I can hesitate offline , but here ... eh)))

Forgive me, please, but could you explain more in detail the technology of storing the rope ladder?)))

- kengu_ry: What if it's a fire? GOD SAVE ME! +

- pitasha: I have also been thinking about the ladder for a long time ... but we live on the 8th floor, shit, I'm afraid there are no such stairs (((((

- kengu_ry: Gagagagag !!! :))) So not only I am crazy :)))

- zoe_dorogaya: hohoho))) this is cool!

and by means of such linguistic tactics as transformation of written discourse into oral one, time is saved and communication is simplified: the time for thinking, writing, verifying the text is reduced, and by deliberate orthoepic twist a specific image of the author is created, the language personality manifests itself by means of such deviations from the norm. Emoticon is an icon, a synonym for the smile concept, which consists of punctuation marks or graphic symbols. This term appeared when the notions "emotion" and "icon" were combined. Since virtual communication involves the absence of such vital for the expression of opinion and attitude phenomena as facial expressions and gestures, emoticons were introduced to solve this problem in online communication. Emoticons have some general rules of construction and are usually read when the image is rotated 90 degrees clockwise. Emoticons denote international concepts, so they do not reproduce current speech, do not reflect grammatical, phonetic, and other features of natural language. Emoticons are a direct tool for forming an impression of the author's position or his personality. Earlier when the field of Internet communication was just beginning to be formed (the main forms of early web communication were conferences and chats), researchers of computer-mediated communication conducted an analysis of the behavior of chat moderators [2]²⁷. As a result, it was revealed that the use of emoticons by moderators contributed to the perception by Internet users as more «dynamic», «friendly», «useful» and «inclined to communicate» compared to those who did not use smiles. Emoticons denote international concepts, so they do not reproduce current speech, do not reflect grammatical, phonetic, and other features of natural language. This study examines the language between people. It is important to understand that human consciousness . This is because each culture interprets body language, gestures, postures and vocalizations differently. This study helps to illustrate the problem studied and the ways in which research findings can be used to better interpret human that speakers regularly use. In this process the role of sociolinguistics, linguistic psychology and cognitive linguistics are important. The study adopted a qualitative research method for data collection and analysis. Using this approach, the study found that there are several meanings associated with the communication or content. The study also shows the disadvantages of anthropocentrism, which happened as a result of using mass media. Basically, the research shows that linguistic personality in human culture is also based on gender. The results of the study led to several recommendations, the most important of which

²⁷ L.Vygotsky. problems of development in structural psychology.-M.,1985

are: people are in the center of the life, everything should serve for them even though the language. More importantly, research suggests that life is dynamic and that some cultural attributes that were fashionable in the past are not so today.

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